

Effect of a calorically restricted dietary regime on oxidative post-translational modifications of plasma proteins in mice and rats

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Abstract : The present investigation studies the effect of a long-term caloric restriction (CR) diet regime on the oxidative post-translational modifications in mouse and rat strains that are reported to exhibit a CR-mediated increase in their lifespan. The level of protein carbonyl formation in the plasma proteins of mice (C57BL/6Nnia) and rats (Fisher 344) under a CR diet investigated with respect to their *ad libitum* (AL) control animals using spectrophotometric, Western blot and/or tritiated sodium borohydride radioactive assay methods demonstrated no association of a long-term CR regime with any retardation in the age-associated increase in carbonylation. The overall level of protein carbonylation was found to be higher in the plasma of CR mice as compared to the respective AL control animals, although this difference was not statistically significant. In the case of rats on a CR diet, the level of carbonylation of two plasma proteins known to be selectively susceptible to oxidative stress in this species, albumin and alpha 1-macroglobulin, was similarly higher than AL control controls but the difference was not statistically significant. Thus, it may be concluded that the increase in lifespan associated with CR in animals across diverse species may not be associated with a universal decrease in oxidative stress. This response may be tissue-specific or may act through modification of other pathways.

Keywords : Calorie restriction, plasma, mice, rats, carbonylation, oxidative stress, oxidative post-translational modifications.

Introduction

Ageing is a complex multifactorial process that is an outcome of alterations at the genetic and physiological level with biochemical consequences at the cellular level. Our comprehension of the mechanism(s) underlying these transformations in cellular and animal models of ageing and age-related disorders is still not clear although scientific knowledge and information in this field has advanced rapidly during the last few decades. Amongst the different strategies proposed to modulate the process of ageing, one of the most accepted non-genetic strategies is restriction of calorie intake. In a calorically restricted (CR) diet regime the total calorie intake is reduced but adequate nutrition is maintained. CR has been shown to delay the ageing process, extend lifespans and diminish the incidences of disease in such diverse experimental species as rodents^{1,2}, rotifers³, nematodes⁴, spiders⁵, fish⁶,

protozoans⁷, yeast^{8,9} and primates as rhesus^{10,11}. Numerous promising reports on the lifespan extension effects with CR have led many people – some of whom are members of the Calorie Restriction Society – to practice a self-imposed CR in an effort to extend their lifespans^{12–14}.

The precise mechanism by which a restricted diet affects the cellular physiology to result in the observed effects across diverse species has still not been properly worked out, although a few hypotheses have been put forward. In view of the numerous reports of lowering of oxidative stress with a CR regime, one of the most favoured hypotheses to explain the positive effects of a CR regime is its lowering of the rate of metabolism¹⁵, thereby diminishing the production of reactive oxygen species and accumulation of oxidative damage^{16,17}. A few recent studies have, however, thrown in a contradictory perception

on the universality of the effect of a CR diet. These reports include those in *Musca*¹⁸, *Ceratitidis capitata*¹⁹ and mice strains as DBA/2^{20,21}, raising questions on the universal applicability of the hypothesis on a favorable effect of a CR regime on different species, different strains of a species and also different tissues of a strain. In view of such a background, the study presented here was aimed at advancing the knowledge and understanding on the relationship between CR and age-associated oxidative post-translational modifications in two mammalian species : mice (C57BL/6Nnia) and rats (Fisher 344). In particular, to test the hypothesis that CR may not universally attenuate the age-associated increase in oxidative post-translational modifications, the level of carbonylation was analyzed in the plasma of two rodent species (mice and rats) which are known to exhibit both a lifespan extension on a CR diet regime^{1,2,20,22-27} and references in ²⁶ and an age-associated accrual of oxidative post-translational modifications in the plasma²⁸. Plasma proteins are known to be exposed to different oxidants under a variety of circumstances *in vivo* as oxidative processes in the extracellular space including tissue injury and inflammation²⁹. In addition, pioneering studies by Stadtman³⁰ has established that the transition metals present in the plasma generate OH• through scission of H₂O₂, leading to formation of protein carbonyls. Plasma is considered to be advantageous as the model tissue for many biochemical studies since it can be collected non-invasively, giving minimum harm to the animals. Therefore, any finding can be readily extrapolated to other animal models for biogerontological studies including age-related disease model studies. In addition, rodents are good model systems for such studies as establishment of homologous genes and processes which extend healthy lifespan can lead to human clinical trials³¹.

Experimental

Chemicals :

Bicinchoninic acid protein assay reagent kit were from Pierce; rabbit anti-2,4-dinitrophenyl (DNP) serum and goat anti-rabbit IgG-horseradish peroxidase conjugate from Zymed; Immunobilon™-P membrane from Millipore; enhanced chemiluminescence immunochemical detection kit from Amersham; standard molecular weight markers of proteins for SDS-PAGE from Novex; and tritiated so-

dium borohydride (NaB³H₄) from NEN Life Science Products, Inc. All other chemicals/reagents were obtained from Sigma Chemical Co., St Louis, MO.

Animals :

Experiments were conducted on male C57BL/6Nnia mice and Fisher 344 rats obtained from National Institute on Aging. Prior to the initiation of CR, all mice consumed a standard NIH-31 diet. Animals were maintained in a pathogen-free environment on a 12-h light/dark cycle, with the light portion beginning at 0630 h.

Caloric restriction :

Starting at 4 months of age, one-half of the animals were randomly assigned to a CR regime according to Dubey *et al.*³² and Kamzalov and Sohal³³ for mice and rats, respectively. The CR diet regimen permitted daily access to 60% of the food consumed by the *ad libitum* (AL) group. The NIH-31 formulation eaten by the CR group animals was enriched in vitamin content in order to balance the intake between the groups. The animals were assessed biochemically at approximately 18–19-months of age ($n = 4-11$ per group). All experiments were conducted in adherence with the NIH guidelines for the Care and Use of Laboratory Animals and were approved by the University of Southern California Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee.

Plasma preparation :

Blood from over-night fasted male mice and rats was collected directly from the hearts of CO₂ euthanized animals, using an EDTA-moistened needle and a syringe containing 50 μL of 100 mM EDTA solution for each ml of blood collected. The samples were centrifuged immediately (within 5–10 min) after collection at 2600 g for 5 min to isolate the plasma.

Measurement of carbonyl content in whole plasma using DNPH :

Total plasma protein carbonyl content was determined spectrophotometrically by the procedure described by Levine *et al.*³⁴. Briefly, plasma samples were treated with 10 mM DNPH solution (prepared in 2 M HCl) at room temperature for 30 min. Proteins were precipitated with 10% (w/v) trichloroacetic acid, and washed with ethanol/ethyl acetate (1 : 1, v/v). The pellet was dissolved in 20 mM Tris/HCl buffer, pH 6.8, containing 0.2% (w/v) SDS

and carbonyl content was measured spectrophotometrically at 370 nm using a molar extinction coefficient of 22 000 M⁻¹ cm⁻¹ for the protein hydrazone derivative³⁵.

Measurement of carbonyl content in whole plasma using tritiated sodium borohydride :

Analysis of oxidative modification of proteins was also performed using tritiated sodium borohydride³⁶. Briefly, plasma samples in 86 mM Tris-HCl buffer, pH 8.6, containing 0.86 mM EDTA were reacted with 50 mM NaB³H₄ for 30 min. The proteins were pelleted with 10% TCA and dissolved in 0.5% SDS/0.1 M NaOH. Radioactivity was measured in a scintillation counter after adding 4 ml of Scintisafe Plus 50% cocktail.

Quantification of carbonyl content of individual proteins :

Dinitrophenyl hydrazine – treated proteins were separated by SDS-PAGE (10% gel) under reducing conditions, according to the method described by Laemmli³⁷, and transferred onto PVDF membrane using the wet transfer procedure³⁸. Immunoblotting was performed essentially as described earlier²⁸. The carbonyl content of individual proteins was determined by densitometric scanning of the immunostained bands in X-ray film using an AlphaImager 2000, manufactured by Alpha Innotech Corp. (San Leandro, CA, USA).

Estimation of protein content :

The protein content was measured using a bicinchoninic acid protein assay kit and BSA as a standard³⁹.

Statistical analysis :

Most of the assay experiments were performed in triplicate assessments with 4–11 animals per group, each animal being treated separately. Results were analyzed for statistical significance with Student's Paired *t*-test for the means and differences in the means with *P* ≤ 0.05 were considered to be significant.

Results and discussion

Objective of this study was to investigate the universality of the phenomenon that a CR regime reduces the level of one of the established markers of oxidative stress, protein carbonyls, in the plasma of different mammalian species. The model species chosen for this study were mice (C57BL/6Nnia) and rats (Fisher 344) in view of

earlier observations wherein an age-associated increase in carbonylation of plasma proteins²⁸ as also CR-associated increases in lifespans^{1,20,22–25} were observed. A CR regime in mice and rats examined was associated with either an increase (statistically insignificant) or no change in the level of carbonylation of plasma proteins. In mice on a CR diet, level of plasma protein carbonyls as estimated using both the spectrophotometric (Fig. 1A) as well as the radioactive method (Fig. 1B) showed no difference in CR animals as compared to the control AL animals. Our earlier findings on selective age-associated carbonylation of some plasma proteins in the rats²⁸ led us to examine the level of carbonylation in the specific tar-

Fig. 1. Quantification of the level of carbonylation of plasma proteins of mice (C57BL/6Nnia) under AL and CR dietary regimes. A : Estimation using spectrophotometric method after derivatization with DNPH (*n* = 10). Fresh plasma as treated with DNPH, pelleted proteins were washed with ethanol : ethyl acetate (1 : 1) and the level of the hydrazone complex was estimated spectrophotometrically at 360 nm. B : Estimation using radiolabelling with tritiated sodium borohydride (*n* = 11). Presented data are mean ± SEM of triplicate measurements of 10–11 independent experiments.

geted proteins only in the AL and CR rats' using Western blotting techniques (Fig. 2). No statistically significant difference in carbonylation of both albumin and alpha 1-macroglobulin in the rats on a CR diet was observed as

diverse range of species, the effect may be mediated by alterations at some fundamental biological process(es). Based on the observation from many laboratories across the world, the hypotheses which have been put forward

Fig. 2. Immunochemical localization of carbonylated proteins in the plasma of rats (Fisher 344) under AL and CR dietary regimes. Fresh plasma was treated with DNPH ($n = 4$); proteins were separated by SDS-PAGE under reducing conditions and transferred onto Immunobilon™-P membranes. Oxidized proteins were detected with anti-DNP antibody and 2nd antibody-HRP conjugate, as described in the Experimental section. (A) Left Panel (Protein staining with Coomassie blue): Lane 1: molecular weight markers; Lane 2: positive control (DNPH treated oxidized BSA); Lane 3: negative control (plasma without DNPH treatment); Lanes 4 and 5: DNPH-treated plasma of AL and CR animals, respectively. (B) Right Panel (Immuno-staining) with same protein loading as left panel. The blot presented here is representative of four experiments.

compared to the AL controls (Fig. 3; Panel A and B). Preliminary determination of carbonyl levels in the plasma of rhesus monkeys ($n = 8-11$) also showed an increase in the CR animals as estimated spectrophotometrically after DNPH derivatization and also using tritiated sodium borohydride method (C. K. Jana and N. Das, unpublished data). However, this increase was also not statistically significant. The main finding of this study is that a CR diet regime does not offset the age-associated increase in carbonylation of the plasma proteins in the mouse and rat strains that were examined. CR diet regime has been found to increase the lifespan of a wide variety of species, transcending phylogenetic borders. The precise mechanism by which a restricted diet affects the cellular physiology to result in the observed effects across diverse species has still not been properly worked out although a few hypotheses have been put forward. However, since caloric restriction prolongs the lifespan of a

to explain the effects of a CR diet regime include that there is (a) a metabolic shift towards increased protein degradation and decreased macromolecular damage through alterations in gene expression^{40,41}; (b) lessening of oxidative damage by reducing the energy flux and metabolism or the “rate of living”^{15,42}; (c) attenuation of oxidative stress-mediated damage to macromolecules⁴³; (d) delay of immunological ageing^{44,45}; (e) decreased free radical generation followed by reduced losses of mitochondria with age^{46,47}; (f) preservation of protein synthesis capacities in old age⁴⁸; (g) neuroendocrine effects^{49,50}; (h) reduction in glycation of proteins⁵¹; (i) decrease in the body temperature associated with a hypometabolic state⁵²; (j) increase in anti-oxidant defense mechanism⁵³; (k) reduced incidence of cancer, tumours and other old-age pathologies⁵⁴⁻⁵⁶; (l) up-regulation of autophagy and apoptosis⁵⁷; (m) reprogramming of energy metabolism^{58,59}; (n) increased angiogenesis⁶⁰ or (o)

Fig. 3. Immunochemical quantitation of the level of carbonylation in the plasma proteins, albumin (A) and alpha 1-macroglobulin (B) in rats (Fisher 344) under AL and CR dietary regimes. Comparisons of the extent of carbonylation were made by densitometric scanning of the immunostained bands in X-ray film. Presented data are mean \pm SEM of triplicate measurements of 4 independent experiments.

decreased iron accumulation⁶¹. These hypotheses are, of course, not mutually exclusive.

There are numerous reports on CR-mediated decrease in level of markers of oxidative stress in diverse species. In mice on CR, carbonylation was reported to decrease in different regions of the brain except the hindbrain³². Reports on the effect of CR on oxidative modifications also include attenuation of increase in age-associated carbonylation of proteins from mitochondria from upper hind limb skeletal muscle of mice⁶². A CR-mediated decrease in protein modification by 4-hydroxy-2-nonenal (HNE) and malondialdehyde (MDA) in the mitochondria of skeletal muscle from C57BL/6 mice but with no effect in DfiBA/2 mice has been reported recently⁶³. However, our results on the plasma proteins of rats and mice did

not show a decrease in carbonyl levels either in whole plasma or in any of the specific protein reported to be susceptible to oxidative stress, which suggests that modulation of oxidative post-translational phenomenon by CR may not be a universal phenomenon. The response may be tissue- and also species-specific. A similar tissue-specific response in the anti-oxidant potential with a CR regime has been reported earlier in mice⁶⁴. However, it may be noted that contrary to our results, a decrease in carbonylation of plasma proteins has been reported in Fisher 344 rats on CR⁶⁵. Differences may be due to variation in animal husbandry/housekeeping and/or CR regime implementation. In spite of the numerous studies on the effect of CR on different tissues of animals of different strains/species, any other report on the effect on the plasma proteins of these or other species were not found. Thus, it is possible that the beneficial effects of CR as postulated by numerous scientists are not demonstrated by a decreased level of protein carbonylation in plasma proteins alone. Therefore, the reported decrease in oxidative post-translational modifications with CR may either be not universal or the effect may not be tissue-wide. In addition, since CR diet regime preserves the protein synthesis rate⁴⁸ but increases turnover^{40,41}, numerous reports of decreased oxidative damage in many tissues examined in diverse organisms may be reflective of summative results of these two phenomena. Turnover mechanism of plasma proteins may also remain unaffected by CR due to reasons beyond the scope of this study. It is possible that various tissues and also that different proteins within each tissue have different turnover rates and that these might also be differentially affected by CR. Further work in this direction is needed to clarify these issues.

The principal aim of this project was to study the effect of a calorically restricted diet on the age-associated oxidative post-translational modifications in a few mammalian species. Mice and rats were used as models for the present study as they are both well studied organisms belonging to the mammalian group and have been previously reported to exhibit increases in their lifespan on a CR diet regime. This study showed no attenuation of the age-associated increase in protein carbonylation in plasma of rats and mice in strains although increases in lifespans of these species/strains have been observed. Our findings

thus suggest that abatement of age-associated oxidative post-translational modifications with CR is not a universal phenomenon and may be tissue- and/or species-specific.

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